

Spectrophotometric Studies of Ferric-esculetin Complex

B. D. Jain and H. B. Singh

Esculetin (6,7-dihydroxycoumarin) has been found to form soluble, coloured complexes at different pH with ferric ions. At pH 9.5 and 394m μ , the complex in 25% methanolic solution obeys Beer's law up to 1.8 p.p.m. of iron (III). Job's method of continued variation and electrophoretic studies have been used to suggest a tentative structure.

Ferron¹, salicylic², and sulphosalicylic acids³ are used for colorimetric estimation of ferric iron. Thiocyanato method⁴, which requires a large excess of the reagent, is applicable in a limited pH range and the colour fades rapidly. Casparious and Manella⁵ first reported the colour reaction of esculetin with ferric iron. It has been shown that iron (III) forms two water-soluble complexes, an unstable green one between pH 0.5 and 4.5 and a comparatively stable red one above pH 7.0. The present studies deal with the latter.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ferric perchlorate (0.001 g. mol./litre) solution was prepared by dissolving ferric hydroxide (obtained by adding alkaline hydrogen peroxide to ferrous ammonium sulphate) in warm perchloric acid. Esculetin, prepared by the method of Amird and Allais⁶, was employed in ethanolic solution (0.001g. mol./litre). Dilute solutions of HCl and NaOH were used for pH adjustment. Unicam spectrophotometer (S. P. 600), Beckman pH meter (H2), and electrophoresis apparatus (B & T) were used.

Absorption Spectrum and Colour of the Complex.—The unstable green complex (pH 0.5-4.5) exhibited maximum absorption at 570 m μ , whereas the red complex (pH > 7) showed a sharp maximum absorption at 394 m μ (Fig. 1). In pH range 4.5-7.0, both maxima were observed. The complex above pH 7.0 was stabilised by 25% methanol and obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.2-1.8 p.p.m. of ferric iron. The intensity of the colour became maximum in the pH range 9.5 to 10.0. A minimum of four-fold concentration of the reagent was required for full colour development and excess was found to cause no interference.

The composition of the complex (Fig. 2), as determined by Vosburgh and Cooper's method⁷, was found to be 1:3. For finding the nature of charge on the complex ion, a drop was placed on a filter paper strip soaked in sodium perchlorate solution at pH 9.5. After applying a constant voltage (220 volts) for half an hour, the strip was developed with pot-

1. Yoe and Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 872.

2. Scott, *Analyst*, 1941, **66**, 142.

3. Lober, *Biochem. Z.*, 1927, **181**, 391.

4. Snell and Snell, "Colorimetric Analysis", Vol. II, 3rd ed., D. Van Nostrand, N. Y., 1954, p. 307.

5. *Hundert Jahre Schweiz. Apoth.-Ver. (Centenaire Soc. Suisse Pharm.)* 1843-1943, **347**; *Chem. Abs.*, 1944, **38**, 1841.

6. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1947, 512.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.

assium ferrocyanide solution. The migration of the complex towards anode showed its negative charge. The following tentative structure is therefore suggested:

FIG. 1. Absorption spectrum.

FIG. 2. Molar composition.

Recommended Procedure and Interference due to Foreign Ions.—The ferric solution after addition of the reagent (about 5 times) and methanol (25% by volume) was adjusted to pH 9.5. Its optical density was measured at 394 mμ and the iron concentration was read from a calibration curve obtained from standard ferric solutions. Due to precipitation of their hydroxides at this high pH, a large number of ~~cations~~ interfered. The limits of concentrations (p.p.m.) of foreign ions that could be tolerated for 2.0 p.p.m. of ferric iron are given below in parenthesis: acetate (2000), bromide (2000), borate (400), chloride (2000), citrate (2000), fluoride (1000), iodide (2000), oxalate (700), phosphate (40), tartrate (600), and thiocyanate (2000).

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